

STUDY THE SATISFACTION LEVEL OF FOREIGN INDIVIDUAL TOURISTS VISITING IN SHIMLA

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Abstract

Tourism satisfaction refers to the sensitive state of visitors after exposure to the experience. It is the post-purchase evaluative judgment and is the outcome of the customer's needs, wants and expectations throughout the product life. It is relevant on the part of the Hill station and heritage destination planners to provide maximum satisfaction to the visitors so that they are the repeat visitors. This paper explores the satisfaction level of foreign tourists visiting at Shimla in Himachal Pradesh. In this paper it has been tried to find those attributes in which tourists were satisfied and dissatisfied. Total 8 demographic variables and 23 satisfaction variables which covering the aspect of general attributed in relation to the tourism, facilities and services. The data were analysed using simple statistical techniques such as Mean, SD and T-test. Mean and SD were used to identify the satisfaction level of respondent. Finally T-test conducted to compare the Demographic variables (Gender). This result would help to improve the standards of the destination.

Keywords: Demographic Characteristics of Tourists, Tourist satisfaction, Destination, Shimla.

Introduction

Today, tourism is appreciated as an economic engine for socio-economic development of many developing nations. Recognising tourism's pivotal contribution in terms of GDP, national income, foreign exchange earnings, employment generation and destination development, more than two dozen countries have inclined to develop and promote tourism in scientific ways.

According to Ministry of Tourism, Government of India (2015) Foreign tourist arrivals in India in 2014 was 7.68 million with the annual growth rate 10.2% in comparison to Indian National departure from India which was 18.33 million with the annual growth rate of 10.3%. The direct contribution of Travel & Tourism to GDP in 2014 was INR 2,478.2 bn (2.2% of GDP). This is forecast to rise by 7.6% to INR 2,667.5bn in 2015.

The tourism industry is a vast industry made up of businesses and organisations that provide goods and services to meet the distinctive needs of tourists. These businesses and organisations are related to virtually all areas of the economy to make tourism as an industry. Interestingly, tourism is an industry of industries.

Indian Tourism is primarily based on culture which contains sites of archaeological interest, historical buildings, monuments, museums, and religious institutions and places of historical importance. On the other hand, festivals, arts and handicraft, music, folk dance. Similarly, Native life and customs are

come under traditional attraction. Scenic attraction are consisting of flora and fauna which may include the places of scenic beauty i.e. mountain, waterfalls, water bodies, rivers, beaches, jungles, desserts snow valley spas etc.

Himachal Pradesh is continues to be one of the most favourite tourism destination for tourists. It had a record arrival of more than 2.1 lakh foreign tourists and 69 lakh domestic tourists during 2005, witnessing a 2% increase in FTAs against 2004. In the similar way tourist's traffic increased during 2009 it had a record arrival of more than 4 lakh foreign tourists and 1.1 crore domestic tourists during 2009, witnessing a 17.5 % rise in FTAs and 6.32 % increase in domestic tourists visits against 2008 figures that are 93.7 lakh domestic tourists and 3.7 lakh foreign tourists . There are observed negative growth, means decrease in the number of tourists in Himachal Pradesh during 2013 1.4 crore domestic tourists and 4.1 lakh foreign tourists witnessing a 17.18% fall in FTAs and 5.7% fall in domestic tourists in the comparison of previous year 2008. In the year of 2014 the total tourist in Himachal Pradesh 1.6 crore, it had a record 7.8% growth on total tourists in comparison of year 2013. (Sources HPTDC 2015).

Shimla a Tourist Hub

Shimla lies in the south western ranges of the Himalayas at. It has an average altitude of 2,397 metres (7,864 ft) above mean sea level and extends along a ridge with seven spurs. The city stretches nearly 9.2 kilometres (5.7 mi) from east to west. The British Territory may have ceased to exist, but its echo lingers on in Shimla (2205m). As the Summer Capital of the British in India, Shimla was the country's focus for the better part of every year and now, is the state capital of Himachal Pradesh. Today, Shimla exists as a well-developed state which contains whole facilities, easy accessibility and numerous attractions making it one of India's most popular hill resorts. Shimla can be visited by the by tourists throughout the year, as each season due to its magical beauty and charm. The snowfall during the winters attracts many tourists and accommodation can prove to be difficult. During summers, everybody wants to escape from the scorching heats of the plains and can enjoy the cool breeze at Shimla and in its vicinity. In summer, Shimla has the attraction of excellent walks and treks against the backdrop of the incredible beauty of wooded ravines, flowers and pines.

Satisfaction

Measuring tourists` satisfaction with a destination is conceptually different from measuring satisfaction at transaction specific level. Moreover, it is contended that while satisfaction at the destination level is influenced by the various transaction that occur at that destination, an individual's level of satisfaction is influenced by much border, global factor, some of which are beyond the capacity of tourism industry to affect. The purpose of this section to outline some ideas that should be taken into account when developing a method to measure satisfaction at this relatively abstract level. The recent studies about cultural/heritage and Himalayan tourism focused on the characteristics of tourists who visited cultural/heritage and Himalayan destination. The study attempts to investigate the relation

between cultural/ heritage and Himalayan destination attributes and tourist`s satisfaction, and to identify the relation between cultural/heritage and Himalayan destination attributes and tourists satisfaction in term of selected tourist`s demographic characteristics and travel behaviour characteristics Tourist`s satisfaction is important to successful destination marketing because it influences the choice of destination, the consumption of products and services, and the decision to return (Kozak& Remington, 2000). Several researchers have studied customer satisfaction and provide theory about tourism (Bramwell, 1998 and Brown 2001). For Example Parasiraman, Zeithaml, and Berry`s (1985) expectation perception gap model, Oliver`s` expectancy- disconfirmation theory. (Pizam, Neumann, and Reichel, 1978) have been used to measure tourists satisfaction with specific tourism destination. In particular, expectancy-disconfirmation has been received the widest acceptance among these theories because it is broadly applicable.

There are a number of reasons why it would be appropriate to look at extending the measurements of tourist`s satisfaction to the more global level of the destination. Whiteout pre-empting the nature of this measurement, these reasons include: Millions of dollar are spend each year on the destination marketing by the National and State tourism offices, airlines and regional tourism bodies. This includes detailed surveys of potential market as well as extensive advertising and promotional campaigns in source countries

Review of Literature - It identifying the void in the existing review of literature in the field of tourist satisfaction, the tourism and hospitality management literature has been focusing on the tourist behaviour aspects of thelast three decade. **Ross and Iso-Ahola (1991)** Explored motivation and satisfaction dimensionsof sightseeing tourist by field study of 225 tourists. The result of this study indicated a considerable amount similarities occur between motivation and tourist`s satisfaction dimensions. **Sekar (2002)** examined the general attributes of visitor satisfaction related to the purpose of visit, mode of arrival, transportation, accommodation, availability of different facilities and quality & sufficiency of services withoverall experience in Mudumalia and Indira Gandhi wildlife sanctuaries of Tamil Nadu. **Angie Driscoll, et.al (1994)** described an exploratory study that tests the consistency of two response formats. These format are originally based on the semantic differential scale and have widely used in the tourism literature to generate measure of perception regarding destination. **Vogt and Fesenmaier (1995)** measured tourists and retailers perceptions of service level in a tourist destination. They use a service quality model to develop survey items and interpret the results. They evaluated a tourism experience by service dimension included reliability, responsive, assurance and access.**Chaudhary (2000)** determined pre and post-trip perception of foreign tourist about India as a tourist destination. She used a gap analysis between expectation and satisfaction levels to identify strengths and weaknesses of India`s tourism related image dimensions so that necessary efforts can be made to ensure that tourist`s expectations are met. **David (2002)** examined the customer`s perception to tourism accreditation. He determine the level

of awareness regarding tourism accreditation amongst the consumer. Further he identified the aspect of accredited operation which are important and they find out the difference in the view of domestic and international or experienced and none experienced. **Debadyati, et.al (2007)** examined the attractiveness of Varanasi as a tourist destination from the perspective of Foreign Tourist. They examine the several demographic characteristic of tourist and their expectation on tourist attributes and satisfaction with the holistic impression of the destination. They carried out the tourist attributes. **Hikaru Hasegawa (2010)** considered a Bayesian estimation of multivariate ordered probit model using a Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) method, which is applied to unit record data on the satisfaction derived from the scenery and meals has the largest influence on the overall satisfaction. **Chand (2013)** investigated the perceptions of resident community of Shimla regarding the environmental respects of Tourism development. Results indicate that residents in Shimla perceive greater negative environment impacts of Tourism than positive one. Despite their awareness of negative impacts they are still support Tourism development.

RESEARCH DESIGN

Objectives of the study

To study the satisfaction level of the foreign individual tourists visiting at Shimla (Himachal Pradesh)

Hypothesis

H1: Tourists are satisfied towards all elements of tourism

H2: There will be no significant difference in the tourist satisfaction level and demographics variables (Gender)

The Study Area

The present study was undertaken in the Shimla. Shimla is the Capital of northern Indian state Himachal Pradesh. It is located at latitude 31°6'12" North and longitude 77°10'20" east. It is situated in the Himalayan foothills.

Methodology

The Sample Size and Data Collection

Data were collected personally by using structured questionnaires from the tourists visiting in Shimla during 15.7.2015 to 15.8.2015. During the survey period 60 tourists were contacted, however 50 tourists were agree to give response and only 25 responses were found correct i.e. 50%. A questionnaire in English contains 8 demographic variables and 23 satisfaction variables covering the aspect of general attributes in relation to the tourism, facilities and services. The variables have been selected on the basis of a survey of previous literature.

Measure

Respondent's opinion was measured on 5-Likert point scale value assigned (5) "Highly Satisfied" to (1) "Highly Dissatisfied". The sampling method was convenient which was designed in such way that it would give an appropriate representation to the study universe. The data were analysed using simple

statistical techniques Such as Mean, SD and T-test. Mean and SD were using to identify the satisfaction level of respondent. Finally T-test conducted to compare the Demographic variables (Gender).

Results and discussion

TABLE 1.1 Demographics Characteristics of the respondents (NO 25)

Variables	Frequency	Valid Percentage (%)
Age Group		
Less than 18	2	8
18-30	19	76
31-45	3	12
46 above	1	4
Gender		
Male	14	56
Female	11	44
Education Level		
10th	1	4
12 th	4	16
Graduate	18	72
Post Graduate	2	8
Marital Status		
Single	18	72
Married	7	28
Other		
Income		

Low	5	20
Middle	17	68
Higher	3	12
Length of stay		
1 day	2	9.4
2-4 day	11	44
5-7 day	9	36
8 or more	3	12

Table 1.2 depicts the various variables of satisfaction level of tourists visiting at Shimla.

Variables	Highly Satisfied		Satisfied		Average		Dissatisfied		Highly Dissatisfied		N.A		Mean	S.D
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%		
Facilities of transportation	2	8	12	48	9	36	2	8					3.5600	.76811
Hotel at destination?	2	8	14	56	9	36							3.7200	.61733
Behaviour hotel staffs	5	20	13	52	7	28							3.9200	.70238
Internal transport facilities	2	8	9	37.5	9	37.5	4	16.7					3.3750	.87539
Traffic maintenance	2	8	7	28	5	20	11	44					3.0000	1.04083
Hygienic condition	3	12	10	40	7	28	5	20					3.4400	.96090
Sanitation	1	4	11	44	9	36	4	16					3.3600	.81035

condition														
Local Food	7	28	11	44	6	24	1	4					3.9600	.84063
Hygienic level of food	5	20	12	48	6	24	2	8					3.800	.86603
Local people Behaviour	8	32	8	32	8	32	1	4					3.9200	.90021
Tourist Information Centre/	4	16.7	10	41.7	7	29.2	2	8.3	1	4.2			3.5833	1.01795
Guide behaviour	6	25	8	33.3	8	33.3	1	4.2	1	4.2			3.7083	1.04170
Convenience for independent	5	20	11	44	8	32	1	4					3.8000	.81650
Rate the service of tour package	1	4.3	15	65.2	6	26.1	1	4.3					3.6957	.63495
Health Facility	3	12.5	4	16.7	14	58.3	1	4.2	2	8.3			3.2083	1.02062
Shopping experience	6	24	12	48	7	28							3.9600	.73485
Shopping facility	4	16	14	56	6	24	1	4					3.8400	.74610
Banking service	5	20	12	48	5	20	3	12					3.7600	.92556
Communication	3	12	8	32	10	40	2	8	2	8			3.3200	1.06927
Security system	5	20	6	24	9	36	3	12	2	8			3.3600	1.18603
Sight scenes around the destination	9	36	14	56	2	8							4.2800	.61373
Purpose of journey is fulfilled	6	24	12	48	6	24			1	4			3.8800	.92736

ranking for destination in comparison to other	6	24	12	48	7	28							3.9600	.73485
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The Following paragraph explain the responses of the tourist`s satisfaction level at Shimla. This study found that the overall (62%) of the tourists were satisfied with all the 23 attributes and (29%) were average and only (9%) tourists` were dissatisfied with all the 23 attributes that I ask in the questionnaire to complete this research work.

Table 3.3 Compare the level of satisfaction between Male and Female

Attributes	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
How do you find Transport	Male	14	3.5000	.65044
	Female	11	3.6364	.92442
Availability of hotel	Male	14	3.7857	.69929
	Female	11	3.6364	.50452
Behaviour of Hotel Staff	Male	14	4.0000	.78446
	Female	11	3.8182	.60302
Internal Transport Facility	Male	13	3.2308	.72501
	Female	11	3.5455	1.03573
Traffic maintenance	Male	14	2.9286	1.14114
	Female	11	3.0909	.94388
Hygienic Condition	Male	14	3.2857	.99449
	Female	11	3.6364	.92442
Sanitation Condition	Male	14	3.2143	.89258
	Female	11	3.5455	.68755
Local Food	Male	14	3.8571	.77033
	Female	11	4.0909	.94388
HygienicLevel of local food	Male	14	3.9286	.91687
	Female	11	3.6364	.80904

Local People Behaviour	Male	14	4.0714	.82874
	Female	11	3.7273	1.00905
HPTDC Resources	Male	13	3.4615	1.12660
	Female	11	3.7273	.90453
Guide Behaviour	Male	13	3.8462	.98710
	Female	11	3.5455	1.12815
Convenience for independent traveller	Male	14	3.8571	.86444
	Female	11	3.7273	.78625
Rate the service of package	Male	13	3.8462	.55470
	Female	10	3.5000	.70711
Health Facility	Male	13	3.1538	1.06819
	Female	11	3.2727	1.00905
Shopping Experience	Male	14	4.0000	.78446
	Female	11	3.9091	.70065
Shopping Facility	Male	14	3.8571	.86444
	Female	11	3.8182	.60302
Banking Service	Male	14	3.8571	.94926
	Female	11	3.6364	.92442
Communication	Male	14	3.3571	1.08182
	Female	11	3.2727	1.10371
Security System	Male	14	3.3571	1.21574
	Female	11	3.3636	1.20605
Sight scenes around Shimla	Male	14	4.1429	.66299
	Female	11	4.4545	.52223
Purpose Of your Journey fulfilled	Male	14	3.8571	.77033
	Female	11	3.9091	1.13618
Rank the destination with comparisons other	Male	14	3.8571	.77033
	Female	11	4.0909	.70065

Table 3.3 Compare the total mean score between Male and Female

	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
total	Male	14	84.2525	20.10375
	Female	11	84.5912	19.81753

$$t = \frac{\bar{x}_1 - \bar{x}_2}{\sqrt{\frac{s_1^2}{n_1} + \frac{s_2^2}{n_2}}}$$

s_2 = SD (female)

n_1 = No. of males

t Test Formula

x_1 = mean (male)

x_2 = mean (female)

s_1 = SD (male)

n_2 = No. of females

$t = - .0421$

The null hypothesis for gender showed no significant difference between male and female tourists since mean score of males was 84.25 (SD=20.10) and that of the females was 84.59 (SD=19.81). The mean difference of 0.33 scores was not statistically significant with a t-test value of - .0421 at 23df (degrees of freedom) and probability not more than .05 at 95 percent.

Conclusions

This paper investigates the tourists` satisfaction at Shimla in Himachal Pradesh and found that overall 63% tourists were satisfied with all the attributes and there are also no significant difference between male and female tourists` satisfaction. The results suggested that the Ministry Of Tourism, Govt. of Himachal Pradesh and Himachal Pradesh Tourism Development Corporation (HPTDC) to improve the service quality as per the tourist` satisfaction in all over Shimla.

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